

Covid 19 Issues - A Disclosure

In this Discussion we will point out all the salient feature of Covid19 Epidemic or Pandemic Issues . As well as a salient features of spreading of Corona Virus within Rural uneducated people . So the Primary Health care knowledge regarding to prevent the Virus spreading as well as initially primary health care centre finally shifting to isolation zone of Covid hospitals .

FULL TEXT LINK :

1. Jaydip Datta , MOLECULAR MODELLING & SIMULATION : A REVIEW FROM

MOLECULAR INFORMATICS , February 2022 , DOI: [10.6084/m9.figshare.12287606.v3](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12287606.v3) .

(https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335919583_MOLECULAR_MODELLING_SIMULATION_A_REVIEW_FROM_MOLECULAR_INFORMATICS?_sg%5B0%5D=dvG-cEz1Q46nyPk7hu0XUv3ly-khmxu3zdzpQlbnxe5d-gZC6YdpuMG8j4pwdQ4XZYWsFpBRDCjW8NjZoaldf3fS73qksyusyqAsM.gtVjHTWuwJjpbuTZsp6IRFHnqpf7FzOi2HgKrzcs_iCokKZOc5mVacV1jpxPyIPKnggmT-vAjUdzeC8vrGDn-w).

2. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/myncbi/jaydip.datta.1/bibliography/public/>

3. JAYDIP DATTA , COVID19 DRUG REVIEW DISCUSSIONS , March 2021

, DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.18899.63525/5](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18899.63525/5) , License [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) .

(https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334139887_COVID19_DRUG_REVIEW_DISCUSSIONS?_sg%5B0%5D=aRFyHw7W3KCCM-9g7udqkRGzJUCw_tCSEXPt-55eIQyvih9nd2zjxvCtME46tl6GvjUkSGAaHrwhdGow33s9j0b-gRTUcOi9lDeEM54w.CnjubrXb-NG4VuEaehu9BEPbhtMM4E91Nylawmgb0665AQXAvPSYX8fknOFKYA3HGzCMMhcBxNOq3FGzMsXFA)